

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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LINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF THE TRANSLATION OF MEMOIRS IN THE EXAMPLE OF JAMES DAVID VANCE'S "A MEMOIR OF A FAMILY AND CULTURE IN CRISIS"

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Abstract

This article describes the social and socioeconomic problems of his hometown of Middletown, Ohio by Ohio Senator J. D. Vance. A Memoir of a Family and Culture in Crisis is a bestselling 2016 memoir is about the Appalachian values of his Kentucky family and the social and socioeconomic problems of his hometown of Middletown, Ohio, where his mother's parents moved when they were young.

Key words: Memoir, author, life story, non-fiction story, memories, linguistic and cultural aspects.

Аннотация

В этой статье сенатор от Огайо Дж. Д. Вэнс описывает социальные и социально-экономические проблемы его родного города Мидлтаун, штат Огайо. Мемуары о семье и культуре в условиях кризиса — это мемуары-бестселлеры 2016 года, посвященные ценностям Аппалачей его семьи из Кентукки и социальным и социально-экономическим проблемам его родного города Мидлтаун, штат Огайо, куда родители его матери переехали, когда они были молоды.

Ключевые слова: Мемуары, автор, жизнеописание, научно-популярный рассказ, воспоминания, лингвокультурологические аспекты.

With increased mobility and migration around the world, narratives about the cross-linguistic experiences of voluntary or involuntary exiles, foreigners, immigrants, and minority populations have become a fashionable genre in the popular press. These autobiographical, fictional, or true stories that focus on the experiences of language learners or multilingual individuals who live in several languages in their daily lives are called "language memoirs." Alice Kaplan, who coined the term in 1994, applies it to people who "learn to speak a new dialect, an ascending language, a language of power or expressiveness in their native language." Notable ancestors are Nabokov's "Speaking Memory", Sartre's "Les" (Words: A Biography of Jean-Paul Sartre) or James David Vance's "A Memoir of a Family and Culture in Crisis". All are written in the first person and feature retrospective accounts of events from childhood, adolescence, or young adulthood. Their authors

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occupy complex authorial/narrative subject positions (James David Vance) because they narrate in another language what is often experienced in one language. They give coherence to events lived in fragments, as seen from the point of view of someone who now fully possesses the language but remembers what it was like when they did not.

A number of descriptive, methodological and structural methods used in the study show that memoir writing undergoes significant changes and is enriched by the general stylistic system of the work through various linguistic forms and internal conceptual frameworks. Allusions to time and place in texts reveal a new non-fictional character. The main goal of the writer is not to enrich the literary language, but to ensure the linguistic uniqueness and individuality of the composition. The flexibility of the genre is enhanced by intertextual appearances. Finally, writing a memoir can have a therapeutic effect on the author.

Fiction writers present stories from the past that are important to future generations. Given its intrinsic cognitive value, this genre significantly expands the cognitive breadth of a person (reader). These texts at the same time reflect the linguistic situation of a certain period, their scientific investigation can be a guide for identifying and studying the linguistic foundations of other genres.

Studying the linguistic layer of the genre of memoir writing, first of all, consists in studying the linguistic mentality of a person (language personality, character), through which both a person and the social environment in which he lives and works are recognized.

This prominent genre, which also includes memoir, continues to evolve today, undergoing significant changes and being enriched not only by its various linguistic forms, but also by its internal conceptual foundations.

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